

QUIZ**LAST NAME: Tizhe****FIRST NAME: Emmanuel****PROGRAM CODE: DMCR****COURSE CODE: ACA-401D****PERIOD NUMBER: 6****INSTRUCTOR: Dr. Gulma**

Edit or delete text to show actual information below:

The author applied US conventions of grammar, usage, and mechanics.

The author used Turabian (footnotes)

The author did use Zotero to insert references

The author used the following software: MSWord 365

QUIZ: A SUMMATIVE ASSESSMENT

- 1. In any research work, the knowledge and ideas of other scholars are often drawn to support or contradict the claims of a researcher. This indicates that other's views are vital in developing arguments in research. Which of these is necessary to do with a reading list when collecting information?**
 - Check for relevant materials using the table of content and index.
 - Locate specific information by skimming through the text.
 - Mark pages with information you need to read closely so that you can return to it.
 - All of the above.¹**
- 2. The use of interviews, questionnaires, and participant observations are common methods used in data collection in research. These are normally analyzed and evaluated in order to arrive at a finding. Which of these presents information for the reader to easily understand, especially when it is a large set of numbers?**

¹ Laurent Cleenewerck and Kabiru Gulma, *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack 1. 2nd ed.* (Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019), 2.

- Analysis by ratio distribution of collected figures in a table.
 - Use of descriptive words to explain the data collected and resulting findings.
 - Use of visual representations in the graphic analysis.**²
 - Writing numbers in both figures and words to describe the data.
3. **The ability of a researcher to write a draft and review its content over and over expresses the thoroughness of a writer. By doing so, the author tries to meet the expectations of the reader. In reviewing the draft, which of these would be unnecessary?**
- Check for blind spots in the argument and try to fill the gap.
 - Review the introduction, conclusion, and claims in the writing.
 - Make sure the body or the report is coherent with the focused topic.
 - None of the above.**³
4. **Writers often try to support their assumptions with evidence from other literature. The writer must acknowledge the authors whose views were used by notifying the reader about the details of the sources. Not doing so, is punishable because**
- It is an academic theft of knowledge through citation which is allowed.
 - It is plagiarism in academic writing which is not allowed.**⁴
 - It is the use of parenthesis in academic work and when not written correctly it becomes wrong.
 - The writer of the source of information used is not a friend.

² Kate L. Turabian, *A Manual for Writers of Research papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition: Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff. Eight edition (Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013), 61-62.

³ Kate L. Turabian, 68

⁴ Cleenewerck and Kabiru, 5

5. **Different methodological approaches are used in qualitative research to collect information for analysis and evaluation. Which of these approaches is most appropriate for an in-depth study of a well-defined situation using multiple data sources?**
- A Narrative approach in research work.
 - A Phenomenological approach in investigative work.
 - A Grounded theory or Ethnological approach in findings.
 - A Case Study approach in academic work.⁵**
6. **The flexibility of qualitative research allows for different kinds of approaches by writers. This is because it does not have strict guidelines and standards for its analysis. What information is required in a qualitative study?**
- Contextual, Demographic, Perceptual, and Theoretical information.⁶**
 - Ethical, Social, Developmental, and Progressive information.
 - Credible, Valuable, Reliable, and Regular Information.
 - All of the above.

⁵ Philip Adu, *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study: National Center for Academic and Dissertation Excellence* (Video Lecture) (The Chicago School of Professional Psychology, 2016).

⁶ Linda Dale Bloomberg and Marie Volpe, *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End* (Los Angeles: Sage Publication 2008), 69–71.

7. **Kate, in her Manual for Writers, encourages the use of a footnote in citing academic work when the institution, department, or instructor has not indicated otherwise. Why?**
- It makes academic work look neat and clean.
 - It is easier for a reader to consult, read, and understand.**⁷
 - It accommodates tables, quoted poetry, or complex formatting.
 - All of the above.
8. **Credibility and authenticity of scholarly work are noticed from the proper citation of other writers' research. What are the elements?**
- The author, title, place, publisher, and year.
 - The rules used in writing the publication, the date, and the page.
 - The place of publication, publisher's name, and date of publication.**⁸
 - The number of literature sources used in the publication.
9. **Preventive Diplomacy failed in resolving conflict in the Democratic Republic of Congo as Swart found out at the end of his research. What were his recommendations for such an approach to be successful in conflict resolution?**
- Use a coalition of military forces from the surrounding nations in times of crisis.
 - Facilitate some negotiation and settlement between the two parties.
 - Employ proper timing in applying Preventive Diplomacy in combination with other strategies of conflict resolution.**⁹
 - Accept no intervention of any external organization.

⁷ Kate L. Turabian, 96

⁸ Ibid, 106

⁹ Gerhardus S. Swart, "The Role of preventive Diplomacy in African Conflicts: A Case Study of the Democratic Republic of Congo, 1998-2004" (Masters diss., Pretoria University, 2008), 256.

10. **The European Union's use of English does not differentiate itself from 'real English' because of its unique terminologies. What is the purpose of the EU style of writing?**

- To facilitate and encourage writing clearly in reader-friendly English.¹⁰**
- To showcase that the European Union is a special and unique commission.
- To differentiate between European and American use of English.
- To demonstrate that the European Union is made up of multiple nations using different dialects thereby necessitating a unified language.

¹⁰ Tom Cooper, John Fallas, Francis Flaherty, John Jones, Tim Martins, Jonathan Stockwell, Julia Townsend, and Peter Workman, eds. *European Commission English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 7th ed. (European Commission, 2011), 1.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

- Adu, Philip. *Writing the Methodology Chapter of a Qualitative Study*. National Center for Academic and Dissertation Excellence (NCADE). (Video Lecture). The Chicago School of Professional Psychology, 2016.
- Bloomberg, Linda Dale, and Marie Volpe. *Completing Your Qualitative Dissertation: A Roadmap from Beginning to End*. Los Angeles: Sage Publication, 2008.
- Cleenewerck, Laurent, and Kabiru Gulma. *ACA-401/ACA-401D Coursepack: Period 1*. 2nd ed. Bangui, Central African Republic: Euclid University, 2019.
- Cooper, Tom, John Fallas, Francis Flaherty, John Jones, Tim Martins, Jonathan Stockwell, Julia Townsend, and Peter Workman, eds. *European Commission English Style Guide: A Handbook for Authors and Translators in the European Commission*, 7th ed. European Commission, 2011.
- Swart, Gerhardus S. "The Role of Preventive Diplomacy in African Conflicts: A Case Study of the Democratic Republic of Congo, 1998-2004." Master's diss., Pretoria University, 2008.
- Turabian, Kate L. *A Manual for Writers of Research Papers, Theses, and Dissertations, Eighth Edition : Chicago Style for Students and Researchers*. Edited by Wayne C. Booth, Gregory G. Colomb, Joseph M. Williams, and University of Chicago Press Staff. Eighth edition. Chicago: University of Chicago Press, 2013.

Cleenewerck, Laurent and Kabiru Abubakar Gulma. 2025. ACA-401/ACA 401D Course Pack: Period 1. 6th ed. Washington, D.C.: Euclid University Press.
<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15245536>.